

IMPROVING THE USE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING TECHNOLOGY IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article describes the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of technology in general secondary schools, the formation of technical creativity in young students.*

Keywords: *science of technology, intellectual projects, creativity, rationalization, invention.*

The Republic of Uzbekistan has chosen and is implementing the path of building a democratic legal state and civil society. The main goal and driving force of the ongoing reconstruction in our republic is the comprehensive development and well-being of a person. In the current period, he brought out the humanization of education and the person-oriented approach to the essence of the content of education.

At the center of this approach is the individual. This approach provides an opportunity to freely choose the content of education. In the process of implementing the person-oriented approach, the educational, spiritual, cultural and life requirements of the person are met. The most important thing is that a humane attitude towards the person is manifested, the individuality of studying in the cultural and educational environment and the ability to act independently are strengthened. A person-oriented approach is aimed at the development of a unity of natural, social and cultural characteristics of a person. Representatives of this approach are I. Ya. Lamer, M. N. Skatkin, V. S. Lednev, B. M. Bim-Bada, A. V. The Petrovskys. As stated by our President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, the fundamental reforms implemented in the field of education in our country today are serving the development of young people, who are considered the future of our country, as mature individuals in all aspects, and their development into competitive personnel.

In the period of rapid development of science and technology of the 21st century, foreign experiences and new projects are entering every field, so they should not feel that they are science teachers in the field of development and education of our country, and they should be able to arouse interest in science in students, having thoroughly mastered this science. In the process of teaching, technology teachers should deeply feel the role and essence of this subject in society, the goals of the subject in education, and at the same time teach students hard work, creativity and, in some sense, entrepreneurship. . "It is known that the teaching profession is a very responsible profession that requires various integrated knowledge and skills.

The teacher of the science of technology, while imparting knowledge to the students in the future, forms skills related to certain professions in them. The teacher must have high qualifications and professional skills in preparing the given items. In order to achieve this result, in addition to knowledge and skills, the teacher must have the ability to influence students through his proven method, education and upbringing. In addition to providing knowledge to students during the lesson, it is necessary to train them in higher education institutions to develop the skills of working and educating them through work. "Technology" plays an important role in introducing students to the world of work and profession. Improving its methodology, strengthening its

material equipment, strengthening the connection of the school with the surrounding industry, organizing socially useful and productive work, increasing its educational and economic efficiency and combining it with education, preparing students for work. improvement is one of the urgent tasks of today. Although the technology lesson uses general didactic principles for other school subjects, it also has its own characteristics. Pupils are not engaged in the activity of knowledge, but in the activity of creation. Subjects, tools, and processes of the science of technology serve not as a simple learning object, but as an instructional tool, didactic material, and a technical tool of education that activates students' work. The science of technology as an educational subject teaches these and other features.

The study of technological science consists of the study of materials, their properties, and various preparation items based on the properties of these materials. This process requires teachers to apply technological knowledge, analyze the quality level of finished products through creative and technical thinking, and impart professional knowledge to students. Teaching students to work from a young age will have a great effect on their future life. Along with working skills, it is necessary to form students' abilities such as creativity, technical knowledge, and collective creativity. The famous idealist philosopher E.L. In one of the most authoritative philosophical dictionaries of the early twentieth century by Radlov, creativity is related to the creation of something, the ability to create is most characteristic of God, and man can only perform relatively creative actions. Along with such statements, attention was paid to the presence of unconscious processes in the creative process.

Later, as the scientific study of various types of creativity changed, so did the attitude towards it in general and the definitions given to creativity. Recently, attention has been focused mainly on the fact that the creation of a new product is related to creativity that did not exist before; creativity is manifested in various spheres of human activity, when new material and spiritual values are created. creativity is an activity that contributes to the creation, discovery of something previously unknown for a specific subject. Another point is related to the scope of creative activity. In social practice, as a rule, creativity is measured by new categories such as discovery, invention, rationalization. Recently, a lot has been said about innovative (innovative) activities related to the introduction of innovations into organizational and technological processes. But such activity can be called rationalization. rationalization - to improve the use of existing technologies (we only consider the aspect related to solving technical problems).

So, we can say this: the inventor is primarily interested in the final effect, the function, the designer - the device that performs the function, and the rationalizer - the more rational use of the finished device for some personal purpose. A rationalization proposal is a solution to a specific problem to improve the performance of a specific problem locally (as opposed to an invention of general importance) in a new specific environment (for example, in some workshops of a factory). but not plant-wide but most production).

In certain cases, a rationalization proposal can be an invention. Design can be 'linked' to the activities of inventors and rationalizers, if their implementation requires the creation of certain designs. The practical difference between invention, design, and rationalization is to be found in the nature of the goals of each activity. The invention is aimed at solving a technical problem, a problem in general; design - creating a structure; A project is a creative solution of an intellectual and practical nature carried out by students. Independent work of students under the guidance of the teacher. If we focus on the working definition of creativity, it is appropriate to associate it with

solving new problems or finding new ways to solve previously solved problems, solving various problems that arise in production, situational difficulties. 'looks and everyday life. Before considering the structure of a creative solution to a new problem, let's dwell on general information about the types of technical creativity. Types of professional creativity include invention, construction, rationalization, design.

There is a close relationship between all types of technical creativity. In the first period of the rapid development of technology, such a division was not observed, and scientific literature mainly talked about inventive activities. Currently, there is a scientific and practical division of the proposal of discovery, invention and rationalization, which are carried out not only in relation to technical objects. Thus, discovery is the establishment of a previously unknown objectively existing property or phenomenon. An invention called a new solution to a problem that has positive value for production, culture, etc. Inventions are divided into structural (devices), technological (methods) and creation of new substances.

It is necessary to form an innovative infrastructure by introducing digital technologies and modern methods into the technological education process. But in order to achieve a high level in this field, first of all, the material and technical base must meet the requirements of the time. To eliminate these shortcomings, the following measures should be taken:

- the content of practical technology taught in general secondary schools is not sufficient for the formation of technological literacy, critical thinking and creativity competencies that can be applied in independent life;
- lack of metasubject competences and interdisciplinary connection in the teaching of technological science;
- in the normative documents of the science of technology, the evaluation criteria are developed only for the competence of the graduate and there is a lack of textbooks, workbooks and teacher's books, multimedia applications, didactic materials;
- the lack of inclusion of elements necessary for the development of the economy of Uzbekistan, such as mechatronics, robotics, electrical engineering, automation, arduino, in the content of the science of technology has a negative effect on the professional qualities of future school graduates and specialists.

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